

Covid-19 Lockdown Health Belief Model-based scale (Cov-19-lock-HBM)

In the following you will find several sentences. Please, indicate how much do you agree with each of them from 0 (I do not agree at all) to 9 (I completely agree).

1. Es probable que me contagie por coronavirus en las próximas semanas/meses.
It is likely that I will get infected with the coronavirus in the next few weeks/months.
 2. Contagiarme por coronavirus es algo que no he considerado.
I did not consider the possibility of catching the coronavirus.
 3. Si percibo a alguien cerca de mí, me siento vulnerable a un contagio por coronavirus.
If I perceive someone near me, I feel vulnerable to a coronavirus infection.
 4. Me preocupa mucho la posibilidad de poder contagiarme por coronavirus.
I am very worried about the possibility of catching the coronavirus.
 5. Temo no poder despedirme de un ser querido si llegara a contagiarme por coronavirus.
I am afraid I won't be able to say goodbye to a loved one if I get infected with the coronavirus.
 6. Respetando la cuarentena evito contagiarme y contagiar a otras personas por coronavirus.
I avoid catching and spreading the coronavirus to others by adhering to the quarantine.
 7. Respetando la cuarentena contribuyo a un bien social común.
I contribute to a common social benefit by adhering to the quarantine.
 8. Siento más soledad desde que comenzó la cuarentena.
I experience more loneliness since the quarantine started.
 9. Desde que comenzó la cuarentena, siento más aburrimiento.
I am more bored since the quarantine started.
 10. Desde que comenzó la cuarentena siento mucha preocupación por mi situación económica.
I am very concerned about my economic situation since the quarantine started.
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Interpretation

Susceptibility: items 1 and 2* (reversed item)

Severity: items 3, 4, and 5

Quarantine Benefits: items 6 and 7

Quarantine Costs: items 8, 9, and 10

Table 1. Exploratory factor analysis

HMB core constructs	Factor 1 (Severity)	Factor 2 (Quarantine Benefits; cf. Webster et al., 2020)	Factor 3 (Quarantine Costs; cf. Brooks et al., 2020)	Factor 4 (Susceptibility)
(1) I am very worried about the possibility of catching the coronavirus.	.816	-.034	.047	.048
(2) If I perceive someone near me, I feel vulnerable to a coronavirus infection.	.614	.186	.043	.092
(3) I'm afraid I won't be able to say goodbye to a loved one if I get infected of coronavirus.	.552	.113	.087	-.019
(4) The quarantine is useful to avoid catching and spreading the coronavirus to others.	.073	.828	-.022	.058
(5) Respecting the quarantine, I contribute to a common social benefit.	.158	.737	-.063	.123
(6) I am more bored since the quarantine started.	-.123	.035	.529	.050
(7) Since the quarantine started, I experience more loneliness.	.166	-.055	.413	.177
(8) Since the quarantine started I am very concerned about my economic situation.	.185	-.058	.319	-.043
(9) It is likely that I will get infected of coronavirus in the next few weeks/months.	.090	.054	-.010	.563
(10) Catching the coronavirus is something that I do not consider.	-.021	.048	.080	.315

Note. $N = 325$. Extraction Method: Principal Axis Factoring. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization. Only item loadings $\geq .3$ were considered within each factor.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

In CFA, several indicators estimate de fitness of the model. The most common are the Comparative Fit Index (CFI), the Tucker-Lewis index (TLI), the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), and the Standardize Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR). CFI and TLI values $\geq .90$ (ideally $\geq .95$), RMSEA $\leq .06$, and SRMR $\leq .08$, indicate good model fitness. The scale showed good indexes CFI = .98, TLI = .97, RMSEA = .026, and SMRM = .045. (See Figure 1).

Figure 1. CFA results

References:

Brooks, S. K., Webster, R. K., Smith, L. E., Woodland, L., Wessely, S., Greenberg, N., & Rubin, G. J. (2020). The psychological impact of quarantine and how to reduce it: rapid review of the evidence. *The lancet*, 395(10227), 912-920.

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